

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE FUNCTION OF THE WORD IN FICTION (BASED ON THE WORKS OF NIZAMI GANJAVI)

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Abstract

The article is devoted to the work of the great poet of the East Nizami Ganjavi. In his work, the power of the impact of speech was analyzed. The role of Nizami in the creation of major lyrical works is noted.

Keywords: ordinary, poetry, the East, poetry, literature, decorative and applied art

Looking at historical sources, these unique, valuable data tell us that people with meaningful, imaginative, clear, concise, effective speech have always been highly valued by society since ancient times, and therefore the personalities of that time have always kept the beauty of speech in the spotlight. Based on these sources, we know that a number of outstanding speakers in ancient Egypt, India, China, Babylonia, Arabia matured precisely before our era, and from these historical sources we also know that the true homeland of the culture of speech, oratory, that is, eloquent and eloquent speech, is Ancient Greece.

In the V-IV centuries BC, the science of "rhetoric" appears, which is experiencing its heyday, speaks about the theory of oratory, proceeding from the historical conditions of its time and developing perfectly during this period. Rhetoric, developed in the senses of the science of beautiful, eloquent speech, oratory, artistic prose, originated in Ancient Greece in the V century BC, there in the III-II centuries BC and entered the system of Rome in the I century BC. Aristotle, Cicero, Quintilian were outstanding theorists of rhetoric, and later the term rhetoric was developed in the meanings of outwardly chic, luxurious, but weak in content and language, simple works, speech, vocabulary [4, p. 101].

Due to the emergence of interest in oratory in the East, the ancient history of culture of the XII-XIII centuries, poets and philosophers of that time Firdousi (934-1024), Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037), Nizami Ganjavi (1141-1209), Sadi Shirazi (1210-1291) and others highly valued the word in their works:

Nədir dil ağızda ey ağılı olan?

Hünər xəzinəsinə açardır inan!

Düşünüb sonra de sözü, müxtəsər,

O qədər danışma, "bəsdir" desinlər –

they valued the science of rhetoric as a special kind of human activity, informing their readers orally with words and expressions that eloquence, the ability to use words are organically linked with human dignity.

In the Ashug poetry of the XVII-XVIII centuries, much attention was paid to the pronunciation of the word, as Shah Ismail Khatai said, preference was given to "the language of Imran - eloquence."

The great playwright of the XIX century M.F.Akhundova cultural speech, oratory, eloquent word, variety of speech, clarity, etc. in his artistic and scientific work, he expressed valuable scientific ideas

and considerations that are very relevant for our time [2, p. 170].

A number of educational statesmen, such as Mirza Kazim Bey, Narimanov, Firudin Bey Kocharli, in their works repeatedly stressed the need to master the high culture of speech. As an example, Hafiz touched upon the issues of eloquence in the second chapter of his work "Fasat and belagat" fanny-essay and methodi-kitabhane "fanny-essay and methodi-kitabhane", published by Sheikhzade Mammad in 1908. The book shows that maranun is the island of Hassan (Gezel-Gokcek), correctly and artistically expressed, and eloquence means that the language can be easily pronounced and written directly and without mistakes. This chapter of the book also mentions the so-called "scientific-semantic" and declarative disciplines, comments on issues such as allegory, metaphor, sarcasm and interpretation, which are special, integral issues that emphasize the beauty of speech [1, p. 15].

The brilliant artist of the Azerbaijani people, the owner of the inexhaustible, incomparable treasure of "Khamse", the mighty pen, the great messenger of art Nizami, who explained the world with language (word), eloquent science, eloquent speech, in this regard touches on quite a lot of issues.

The views of the outstanding scientist, academician, philologist Arasli on this brilliant artist are very remarkable: "in connection with these issues, the poet speaks about the height of mastery, praising the power and power of the artistic word, defining the tasks facing his art." Taking into account the poet's interesting ideas about the art of words, we can say that the poems of such an artist are full of deep meanings, it is necessary not only to look at what the artist has contributed to his definition of language, words, but also to consider his thoughts about the science of eloquence and eloquence, which have deep scientific and philosophical significance, as ideas, having a more grandiose, meaningful meaning than it seems [3, p. 23].

The science and laws of rhetoric, the art of speech, the role of beautiful speech in human society, etc. His valuable thoughts about Allah Almighty are also confirmed by his statements in the 17th verse of Surah Yasin The Qur'an sent down to us by the Almighty: "vamaaleina illalal balagul Mubin (I untied the knot in your language so that they would understand you).

According to the order, the Word is Holy, and the master who polishes the word is the holy of holies. If we reveal the precious value that the poet attaches to the word, the word makes you laugh, the word makes you cry, the word pleases, upsets, and gives hope, and destroys hope. The brilliant Iranian poet Firdousi, whom the poet greatly appreciated, often referred to his name in his works, wrote a thousand years ago: “appreciate the word, but in life the word remains in memory:

Qələm ki, bu həyatda tərpnənək ilk dəfə
Sözdən yazdı, diqqətlə baxsan birinci hərfə.
Yalnız sözlə qazandı kainat bu şöhrəti,
Bir bu qədər dedilər azalmadı qiyməti” [5, p. 434].

In these verses, our poet, who considers the word the most valuable, coordinates the ideas that he carries in the “Treasury of secrets” with the ideas of Firdousi, whom he often mentions with deep respect in his works.

Mənəm ol, şahi-məani ki, fəzilətim əyandır,
Yer ilə zəmanə hakim hünərim bir asimandır.
Nəfəsim tutub cahanı uca səslə zəngə bənzər,
Qələmimsə bayraq olmuş o da fətehi-cahandır [5, p. 34]

in his oath, which begins with verses, he wanted to express that his poems with subtle spiritual pleasures sound from all sides, showing that his powerful pen is a flag that conquers countries, and that he is the king of the unique world of art created by him.

Günəşim fələkdə parlar, o şafəq saçır cahana
Cəsədim Məsihdəmdir, o həyat bağışlayandır [5, p. 34].

The poet, the owner of a mysterious pen, with these stanzas wants to convey the greatness of the power of influence of his inexhaustible art (according to legend, Jesus is also Christ – His nickname is on the fourth layer of the sky, like the sun), calling himself a breathing Christ, giving life to the dead, shining like the sun, and radiating indignation. Let’s pay attention to the following stanza:

Ürəyim Məsih otağı kərəmülkitab söz ilə
O möhürlənib gözəlcə, bu möhür ona nişandır [5, p. 34].

With these verses, the poet with fine taste compares his creations with our holy book the Koran, rich in its unique wisdom, each verse of which is read with eloquence. Since the Quran is considered the last of all the holy scriptures in the Islamic world, the poet also wants to declare with his works that he has completed the art of the word and thereby gained eternity. According to his writings, it is safe to say that the remarkable owner of the Nizami pen, who highly appreciated the art of speech, possessed oratorical skills, the perfection of speech, its culture, the power of speech and a number of unique scientific and theoretical ideas and considerations. Appreciating the art of the word, the guardian of the word Nizami in his chapter “treasure of secrets” about the word, which he called “the power of the word”, praised the word, adding the most worthy words to his fun:

Sordu: Köhnə qızılı, təzə sözmü yaxşıdır?
Söz sərəfi söylədi: “Söz dünyanın naxışdır” [5, p. 34]

he appreciated the idea that the word opens his eyes to the world for the first time, singing in a powerful poetic language that the word has a wonderful power in human life.

The wise phrases in the “treasury of secrets”, rich in its infinite values, indicate that the poet was well acquainted with the science of eloquence, and the poet, who constantly appreciated this beautiful science in his own words, used beautiful phrases that struck the heart with other poems.

Mən özüm fəhahət ilə oxusam zəburu hərgah,
Kəsərəm o möbüdün, bil dilini ki, zəndxandır [5, p. 34].

With these subtle emotional verses written in this part of the fable, the poet compares his works with the sacred psalms of David, emphasizing that they have no equal in terms of eloquence, that is, he wants to say that if I read my poems with eloquence, I will silence the gods who sing, thereby giving to understand that the poet has the ability to outshine the artists who came before him, he insistently wanted to be noticed.

Qəzəlim qulaqlar üçün verər ağığamın nəvası
Üzü lalə rəngli meytək əsərim ürək açandır.
Dəfi çalmaram səbəbsiz, toy olar, təbil çalarsan
Sözümün yanında sözsüz nə ki, çalğı var yalandır.
Əsərim şikəst də olsa o təbii bir gözəldir,
Şirəmin nə xıltı varsa, yenə də o, nuşi-candır [5, p. 34].

The Arghamın is a wind instrument of that time, its sound is carried across the sky when playing, and in this work the poet wanted to emphasize such features of his works as conciseness, and in the next stanza the poet extracts juice from all the sciences of his time and puts it into his work, stating that the waste of this juice is useful for various fields of science and art.

It should also be noted that we divide any historical period into periods such as the Nizami period, the Nasimi period, the Fuzuli period, and so on, considering the spiritual world as a period. An example of this is the military leaders and rulers who lived in the time of Nizami, famous and revered for their works, in which the poet refers to historical moments created by his powerful pen. For example, in “Alexandria”, where he touched on the interesting moments of the life of Alexander, the powerful Macedonian ruler who conquered half of the ordinary world, along with the philosophers of antiquity, he characterized him as a thinker, visionary, possessing deep wisdom, creating the image of an orator with an eloquent speech, because the most difficult works in the world can be performed by sages, masters words and speakers thanks to deep wisdom and the order of pen ownership. Let’s take a look at a small piece of work:

Ona rast gələndə bir qatı düşməni,
Vuruşda işləri bərkə düşərkən
Əvvəlcə qızılı işə salardı,
Qızıltək işləri tez həll olardı.
Qızıl iş görməsə, iş olsa mahal,
Qılınca atardı əlini dərhal.
Qılınca etməsəydi bu işə çarə,
İşi tapşırırdı əfsunçulara.
Bir iş görməsəydi onlar da ağər,
Köməyə gələrdi onda nətiqlər [5, p. 524].

Nizami in “Iskender-nama” with these stanzas especially notes Alexander’s use of the power of the word, one of the means of struggle: the word plays an important role in a matter that gold, sword, spells cannot solve, and is

considered more effective and powerful than all means, Besides the fact that it is considered strong, reliable.

The outstanding scientist and researcher Radig in his book "The History of Ancient Greek Literature" recorded an interesting fact from the life of Alexander the Great: "Alexander the Great not only used speakers for this purpose, but also made very serious, touching speeches himself. In this sense, the use of this word also occupies a certain place in his field practice. So, one of his speeches eliminated the desertion moods of soldiers who were tired of traveling to foreign countries, mired in homesickness, relatives and friends, demanded to return home, which led to their re-mobilization and reunification around Alexander" [6, pp. 356-372].

Namely, based on these historical data, he often connects the strength and abilities of Alexander the Great with his language, eloquence. The reason for this, as noted in the work, was that Alexander studied with his father and teacher Nikumash, the outstanding Greek philosopher and scientist Aristotle (Nikumash was in the service of the Macedonian rulers of Aminta, the father of the famous philosopher Aristotle, and then Alexander's father, Philip).

Tarixin yığılmış tumarlığından

Keçmiş belə nəql edir bir dehqan:

(In this verse, dehgan is used in the sense of vil-lager)

Elə ki, Feyləqus təzə gəlintək

Vurdu bu dünyanın mülkünə bəzək [5, p. 409].

Feylagus – it is also called Filigus. Alexander the Great's father was Philip, who reigned in 359-336 BC.

Ağıllı övladla ata fəxr edər

Çünki mübarəkdir seçilmiş gövhər.

Oturtdu öyrənsin ədəblə hünər,

Günəş eylər daşı qiymətli gövhər.

Niqumaş alimdir, biliklə dolu,

Alimin oğluydu həkim Ərəstu [5, p. 409].

Aristotle (Aristotalis was the famous ancient Greek philosopher and scholar-encyclopedist), who lived in 384-321 BC, the son of Nicomachus, a scientist

who was the teacher of Alexander the Great and was his fellow student, childhood friend and mentor for both of them.

Addressing these historical moments in the work, Nizami filters out the eloquent speech of Nigumash from his wonderful pen:

Yəqindi bilikli həkim ustadə,

Tacidar olacaq bir gün şahzadə.

Onun təliminə verdi çox diqqət

Kişini şad edər qorusa sər-vət.

Oğlunu tapşırdı gənc şahzadəyə

And verdi, söz aldı "Peyman ver" deyə.

In the following stanzas, the touching speech of the scientist Nikumash, who gave Alexander the knowledge of science and life, confidently inspires that only Arastu, the young prince, and later King Jahan, will help Alexander in his ways of governing the state as a faithful vizier.

Onunla et çətin işdə məşvərət,

Qızıldan kəskindir, gözəl məsləhət [5, p. 409-410].

Quite logical and effective is the appeal of the young prince, who appreciates the eloquent speech of the poet in the section "Sharafnam" "Iskendername", in which the king of Iran, Dara, arranges his speech with a letter that Alexander wrote to Dara before starting the battle.

References:

1. Abdullayev N., Məmmədov Z. Nitq mədəniyyətinin əsasları. Bakı, 2005.
2. Axundov M.F. Əsərləri. 5 cild. Bakı, Azərnəşr, 1951.
3. Araslı H. Nizami Gəncəvi. Bakı, Azərnəşr, 1947.
4. Həsənov H. Nitq mədəniyyəti və üslubiyatı. Bakı, 2013.
5. Klassik Azərbaycan ədəbiyyatı kitabxanası. XX cild. N.Gəncəvi. Bakı, 1961.
6. Радциг С.И. История древне-греческой литературы. Москва, 1969.